

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18208469>

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CONTINUITY OF PROFESSIONAL LIFE IN OLD AGE: EXPERIENCES OF OLDER WOMEN IN URBAN AND RURAL LABOR MARKETS IN LITHUANIA

Abstract

The article analyses aspects of continuity of professional life of older women in Lithuanian cities and rural areas. The aim of the study is to reveal how the professional stability of women aged 45–55 is related to formal and informally acquired social and digital skills, and how the recognition of these skills is determined by the mechanisms of social capital and symbolic power. Based on the theories of social capital and skills development, it is planned to investigate the differences in skills acquisition, application and recognition in urban and rural contexts. The study plans to apply a mixed method – a quantitative survey (1500–2500 women) and qualitative interviews. The results of the study will contribute to the improvement of active ageing, gender equality and regional policy in Lithuania.

Keywords: professional continuity, older women, social skills, digital skills, social capital, regional inequality.

Introduction

Rapid population aging trends are becoming evident in Europe, driven by low birth rates and increasing life expectancy. Population aging and related challenges in the labour market are particularly relevant in Lithuania, where the rate of population aging is almost twice as fast as the European Union average (Strata, 2020) and by 2030 more than a third of the Lithuanian population will be over 55 years old (LR Statistics Department, 2023), therefore a significant decrease in the labour force is predicted by 2070 (Kairys, 2023).

These trends necessitate a deeper study of the factors that ensure the professional activity and stability of older workers. Studies show that the labour market participation rate begins to decrease in the 45–54-year-old age group (Lengvinienė et al., 2014). The group of women in this age group is particularly vulnerable and economically insecure. Statistical data confirms this. In 2022 The employment rate of women in Lithuania in the 45–54 age group reaches about 78–80 percent, but already in the 55–64 age group it decreases to 57–60 percent. (Eurostat, 2023). Unemployment among women aged 45 and over was 2.5 p.p. higher than among women aged 30 or 40 and 0.2 p.p. higher than among women aged 60 (Statistics Department of the Republic of Lithuania, 2023). It is from the age of 45 that working-age people experience difficulties in the labour market - employers provide less opportunities for skill development, it becomes increasingly difficult to find the desired job, and self-confidence decreases (Brazienė, 2017). Women aged 45–54 move from the peak of professional activity to the stage of maturity, in which they assume responsibility for elderly relatives and adolescent children (Mussida et al., 2020, Perrig-Chiello et al., 2008). Due to family obligations, women's networking

opportunities are decreasing (Wanigasekara, 2016), and a lack of technological competencies is becoming evident (Bendick et al., 2010, Sederevičiūtė-Pačiauskienė, 2014).

From a regional perspective, these problems are even more relevant due to slow job creation, insufficient labour mobility, mismatch between the need for qualified labor and the possibilities of meeting it (Dromantienė, 2008), insufficient network of schools and other social services (Grigužauskaitė, 2021), unevenly developed education in regions, low motivation of older people and people living in regions to learn (Valstybės kontrolė, 2023), fewer opportunities to develop networking and accumulate social capital due to structural exclusion and personal hesitation (Greguletz et al., 2018). Judging by statistical data, employment grew fastest in the long term in the group of large regions of the country, slowest in the smallest territories of the country, significant inequalities in the development of the number of employed people in regional groups emerged (Okunevičiūtė-Neveauskienė et al., 2019), which have remained almost unchanged over many years (6.2 percent in 2014, 5.9 percent in 2020) (Ministry of the Interior of the Republic of Lithuania, 2022). The employment rate of women in the Vilnius region in 2023 reached 61.5 percent, while in the Central and Western Lithuania region – 52 percent, i.e., 9.5 p.p. lower than in the capital region (Eures, 2023).

The relevance and scientific novelty of this study is related to the interdisciplinary approach – the study seeks to integrate and comprehensively study several essential perspectives of social sciences. These perspectives include an in-depth analysis of social capital theory based on Coleman, Putnam, revealing the mechanisms of symbolic power (Bourdieu, Foucault), the need for a set of skills and the deep expressions of regional inequality. There is still a lack of comprehensive research in Lithuanian scientific literature. Previous works, although valuable (Ciegis et al., 2013, on sustainable development; Poviliūnas, 2005, on social inclusion policy; Kairys et al., 2016 on the well-being of older people), mostly examined these aspects separately or in a more general context.

The problem is that despite the population aging trends, higher female unemployment in the regions and the resulting need to ensure professional stability in older age, there is still a lack of comprehensive research that would help systematically analyse and reveal how the professional stability of women aged 45–55 in urban and rural labour markets is related to formal and informally acquired social and digital skills and how the recognition of these skills is related to the mechanisms of social capital and symbolic power. In the absence of systematic analysis data, it remains unclear what the fundamental reasons for the decline in professional activity of women aged 45–55 are and how to effectively strengthen it at the regional level.

The planned object of the study is the formal and informally acquired social and digital skills of women aged 45–55 that are important for their professional stability in different regional contexts – urban and rural.

The planned aim of the study is to investigate how the professional stability of women aged 45–55 in urban and rural labour markets is related to formal and

informally acquired social and digital skills and how the recognition of these skills is determined by the mechanisms of social capital and symbolic power.

Planned research objectives:

1. Based on the theoretical provisions of social capital and symbolic power, to conceptualize the connections between the totality of social and digital skills and professional stability in the context of the labour market of older women in the regions.

2. Based on theoretical concepts of skills and models of professional stability, to identify and systematically analyse the factors shaping the professional stability of women aged 45–55 and determining the development and recognition of skills.

3. Conduct an empirical study that would explain how skills are acquired and applied by women aged 45–55 in urban and rural contexts, and would reveal how mechanisms of social capital and symbolic power determine the value and recognition of these skills in different regions.

Literature review

In Lithuania, the proportion of older people in the overall population is increasing (Vilkoitytė et al., 2020), with women making up the majority of the elderly, as they live longer on average than men (Samuels et al., 2018). Another important trend is the declining population in towns and villages (Pociūtė-Sereikienė et al., 2019). As a result of these processes, the number of working-age individuals is decreasing, while the relative share of older people is increasing (Lengvinienė et al., 2016). Given these demographic trends, it is particularly important to examine the factors that ensure professional stability and continuity in mature age. In the context of the labour market, social aging plays a significant role, as self-perception changes, social roles evolve, and relationships shift both in society and within the family (Garlauskaitė et al., 2015). Age is important not only as a chronological marker but also as a set of accumulated experiences, social expectations, and cultural norms, which can either strengthen or limit career resilience (Settersten, 2003). Research shows that women's age is directly related to their career outlook: women at 40 are determined to maintain current life structures, those aged 40–50 feel they are at a turning point, while women at 50 describe initiating major life changes related to self-discovery (Gersick et al., 2015). At older ages, people are more likely to view their careers as personally meaningful due to increased awareness and lifelong autonomous role choices that increasingly align with their personal needs (Goštautaitė et al., 2020). In seeking meaningful careers, older women face challenges in providing care for grandchildren, spouses, other relatives, friends, and communities (Samuels et al., 2018). Their higher risk of social exclusion should be understood as a consequence of the life course, where the lack of adequate work–life balance policies lead to gendered inactivity periods during working age (Botti et al., 2011). Older age becomes a barrier to successful labour market participation due to age discrimination, health problems, and a lack of appropriate or modern skills (Brazienė R., 2017). Although age and its related challenges are important, individual competencies are crucial for successful labour market participation. Therefore, it is important to analyse the concept and classification of skills.

In scientific literature, a skill is understood as an automated action of thought and practical activity, formed through practice and developed over time (Jovaiša, 2007), and can be acquired both formally and informally (Johnson et al., 2022). Several areas of skill development are distinguished: thinking (creativity and innovation, critical thinking, problem-solving, learning to learn), ways of working (communication, collaboration, teamwork), tools for working (information and technological literacy), and living in the real world (citizenship, career, responsibility) (Mawas et al., 2018). Due to technological progress and the emergence of artificial intelligence, digital skills are essential for ensuring economic resilience (Fasbender et al., 2023), as they are linked to the reliable and critical use of content created by the information society in the workplace. The use of technologies should strengthen critical thinking, creativity, and foster innovation (Salienė, 2009). Studies confirm that the percentage of older adults in Lithuania capable of solving problems in technology-rich environments is significantly lower than among youth, with rural residents participating in training especially rarely (Moskvina, 2020). Beyond individual skills, the ability to effectively apply and consolidate them in the labour market also depends on the broader social context. In this context, social capital and its connections with symbolic power become particularly important.

Coleman's concept of social capital encompasses relationships, support, trust, information sharing, and the cohesive power of effective norms; Putnam introduces the idea of social capital as both bonding and bridging (Armakauskaitė, 2024); Bourdieu defines social capital as a network of social relations, argues that power can be possessed, and analyzes its resources (Gečienė, 2002). Highlighting the essence of symbolic power, Bourdieu vividly and precisely calls it "invisible," "unrecognized" power (Kuznecovienė, 2000); Foucault, meanwhile, insists that power is not the property of individuals or groups (Gečienė, 2002). The development of social capital in urban and rural areas and communities remains a subject of debate and scholarly research (Ellison et al., 2014). Social capital complements traditional economic resources and enhances the ability to create new knowledge (Pylipenko et al., 2023), which is why social skills – a complex of personal traits enabling easy communication with others (Gudžinskienė et al., 2023) – are essential in today's labour market.

To summarize the literature review, demographic trends in Lithuania pose significant challenges to the labour market, particularly regarding the professional stability of older women. Successful participation in the labour market depends not only on digital and social skills acquired formally and informally but also on social capital, which can contribute to the formation of symbolic power. Although international and national studies widely examine the impact of aging, skills, and social capital, there is a lack of complex research that systematically analyses the interconnections of these factors with the professional stability of women aged 45–55 in different regional contexts (urban and rural). This study seeks to fill this gap by providing a more comprehensive perspective on the significance of these factors for the labour market stability of women aged 45–55, the peculiarities of skill acquisition and recognition, the factors that promote or hinder skill development and recognition,

and the mechanisms of social capital and symbolic power in Lithuania's urban and rural labour markets.

Methodology

The study will apply a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative methods to collect comprehensive data on the formally and informally acquired social and digital skills of women aged 45–55, which are significant for their professional stability in different regional contexts – urban and rural.

Planned Research Objectives:

1. To identify which skills women aged 45–55 consider most important for labour market stability.
2. To reveal the factors that facilitate or hinder the development and recognition of these skills.
3. To analyse how these skills are acquired and applied in urban and rural contexts.
4. To uncover which factors (structural, cultural, institutional) determine women's opportunities to participate in training and consolidate skills.
5. To assess how the value and recognition of skills differ between the centre and the periphery.

Planned Research Methods:

1. **Qualitative research:** semi-structured interviews and the strategic foresight method through focus groups with older women. The sample will include women aged 45–55 from different professions and sectors (public, private), with different employment types (employment contracts, self-employment). The sample size will be 30–50 women from urban areas (structured according to Eurostat classification: metropolitan/cities, suburbs, rural areas) and 30–50 women from rural areas or small towns.

2. **Quantitative research:** a survey focused on the skills, self-esteem, learning experiences, and professional security of women aged 45–55, with a clear urban/rural comparison. The sample size will be 1,500–2,500 women (structured according to Eurostat classification: metropolitan/cities, suburbs, rural areas).

Respondents will be recruited in cooperation with the Employment Service, employer organizations, NGOs, and through social networks. The duration of both qualitative and quantitative interviews (respondent time) will be 30–40 minutes. Qualitative data will be analysed using thematic and narrative analysis, while quantitative data will be analysed using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and other methods.

The study will adhere to the following ethical principles: respect for personal privacy, confidentiality and anonymity, benevolence and commitment to do no harm to participants, and fairness.

Expected scientific and practical significance

It is anticipated that the study will enrich theoretical knowledge about the interconnections between social capital, symbolic power, and the recognition of skills in Lithuania's regional contexts. From a practical perspective, the results could contribute to the improvement of active aging and gender equality policies, enhance

the effectiveness of regional development strategies, encourage the participation of older women in the labour market, and promote lifelong learning.

Conclusions

This planned study seeks to systematically reveal the links between the professional stability of women aged 45–55 and their social and digital skills, as well as factors of social capital. The interdisciplinary approach will allow for the integration of social, economic, and cultural perspectives, while the results will contribute to scientific discussions on active aging and regional equality in Lithuania.

The article has been prepared on the basis of a doctoral research proposal. The study is planned to be carried out at the Lithuanian Centre for Social Sciences during 2025–2029.

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